

Accelerating effect of arsonium ylide for the copolymerization of acrylonitrile and α -methyl styrene

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Abstract : *p*-Acetyl benzylidene triphenyl arsonium ylide (*p*-ABTAY) accelerates α,α -azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN) initiated copolymerization of acrylonitrile (AN) and α -methyl styrene (α -MS) in DMF at 65 ± 0.1 °C by reducing the rate of termination. The value of energy of activation in the presence and absence of *p*-ABTAY is 11.0 and 9.8 kJ/mol, respectively.

Keywords : Copolymerization, *p*-ABTAY, rate of polymerization intrinsic viscosity.

Introduction

The stereo specific polymerization of various acrylates has been studied by using a variety of initiators such as triphenyl phosphine and iron(III) complex¹, thiol², the D-glucose ceric ion redox system³, benzoyl peroxide⁴, tert-hexylperoxyvalate⁵ and fullerene⁶. Some ylides, containing non metals like nitrogen⁷⁻¹⁰, sulphur¹¹, phosphorus¹² and arsenic¹³ have also been used for polymerization of vinyl monomers. The properties of ylides are very much dependent on the identity of the hetero atom. The dipolar and nucleophilic character of the ylides appear to increase their stability.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile (AN) and α -methyl styrene (α -MS) were purified, distilled and dried according to the standard methods¹⁴. The ylide (*p*-ABTAY) was prepared by the method given in the literature¹⁵. The ylide is insoluble in non polar solvents like benzene and carbon tetrachloride but partially soluble in (> 10%) polar solvents like dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) and dimethyl formamide (DMF). Polymerization was carried out at 65 °C by employing a modified dilatometric apparatus¹⁶ using DMF as an inert solvent for 105 min. The progress of reaction was monitored with the help of cathetometer as meniscus movement (per unit volume per unit time). The copolymer was precipitated with diethyl ether/*n*-hexane (2 : 1) mixture and were dried to a constant weight. The copolymer was soluble in THF. The percentage conversion data were

used to calculate the rate of copolymerization. The intrinsic viscosity of the polymer in tetrahydrofuran solution were measured at 30 °C using ubbeholde viscometer.

Results and discussion

The result of kinetic investigation of copolymerization of AN and α -MS initiated by AIBN with DMF as an inert solvent in the presence of *p*-ABTAY at 65 ± 0.1 °C are summarized below.

The influence of [*p*-ABTAY] has been studied by varying its concentration from 0.74×10^{-3} to 4.40×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹ while keeping [α -MS] (1.66 mol L⁻¹) and [AN] (3.29 mol L⁻¹) constant. A study of Table 1 states that [*p*-ABTAY], accelerates the rate of copolymerization. The order of reaction with respect to [*p*-ABTAY], determined from the linear part of the slope of the plot between log R_p and log [*p*-ABTAY], is 0.25. The value for the intrinsic viscosity decreases as the [*p*-ABTAY] increases.

The influence of [AN] on the rate of polymerization was studied by varying [AN] from 0.82 to 3.29 mol L⁻¹, while keeping [*p*-ABTAY] (0.74×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹) and [α -MS] (1.66 mol L⁻¹) constant. The monomer exponent value, calculated from the slope of linear plot of log R_p and log [AN] was found to be 0.90.

The effect of [α -MS] on the copolymerization of α -MS and AN has been studied by varying [α -MS] from 0.41 to 1.66 mol L⁻¹, while keeping [AN] (3.29 mol L⁻¹) and [*p*-ABTAY] (0.74×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹) constant. The monomer exponent value with respect to [α -MS] has

Table 1. Effect of [*p*-ABTAY] on percent conversion, rate of copolymerization and intrinsic viscosity for the radical copolymerization^a of α -methyl styrene and acrylonitrile

Run no.	[<i>p</i> -ABTAY] $\times 10^3$ (mol L ⁻¹)	Percent conversion	$R_p \times 10^4$ (mol L ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	η
1.	0.00	16.90	3.20	0.025
2.	0.74	17.30	3.27	0.029
3.	1.48	17.80	3.27	0.032
4.	2.22	17.90	3.38	-
5.	2.96	18.10	3.42	0.050
6.	3.70	18.30	3.46	0.090
7.	4.44	19.00	3.59	-
8.	5.18	19.60	3.71	0.140
9.	5.92	21.00	3.97	0.190
10.	6.66	21.20	4.01	-
11.	7.40	21.50	4.07	0.270

^a[AN] = 3.29 mol L⁻¹, [α -MS] = 1.66 mol L⁻¹, [AIBN] = 11.08 $\times 10^{-2}$ L⁻¹, Temp. = 65 \pm 0.1 $^{\circ}$ C, time = 105 min.

been calculated from the slope of the plot of log R_p vs log [α -MS] as unity.

The effect of [AIBN] on R_p has been studied by varying AIBN from 2.77×10^{-2} to 11.08×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹ keeping [α -MS] (1.66 mol L⁻¹), [AN] (3.29 mol L⁻¹) and [*p*-ABTAY] (0.74×10^{-3} mol L⁻¹) constant (Table 2). The order of reaction with respect to AIBN, calculated from the slope of linear plot between log R_p and log [AIBN] was 0.42. This value is less than 0.5

Table 2. Effect of [AIBN] on percent conversion, rate of copolymerization and intrinsic viscosity for the radical copolymerization^a of α -methyl styrene and acrylonitrile

Run no.	[AIBN] $\times 10^2$ (mol L ⁻¹)	Percent conversion	$R_p \times 10^4$ (mol L ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	η
1.	2.77	9.58	1.81	0.007
2.	5.54	13.30	2.52	0.010
3.	8.31	16.30	3.08	-
4.	11.08	17.30	3.27	0.029

^a[AN] = 3.29 mol L⁻¹, [α -MS] = 1.66 mol L⁻¹, [*p*-ABTAY] = 0.74×10^{-3} L⁻¹, Temp. = 65 \pm 0.1 $^{\circ}$ C, time = 105 min.

which supports accelerating effect of *p*-ABTAY.

The influence of temperature on the R_p has been studied at three different temperatures i.e. 60, 65 and 70 $^{\circ}$ C. The R_p was a direct function of temperature. The value for the energy of activation in the presence of (*p*-ABTAY), calculated from the Arrhenius plot was 9.80 kJ mol⁻¹ is lower than the value obtained in the absence of [*p*-ABTAY] i.e. 11.0 kJ mol⁻¹. The comparative low value of energy of activation in the presence of (*p*-ABTAY) further confirms the accelerating nature of (*p*-ABTAY). The accelerating effect of *p*-ABTAY was expected due to any of the following reasons :

- (i) Due to increase in rate of initiation (R_i) or rate of propagation (R_p).
- (ii) Due to decrease in rate of termination (R_t).

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of AIBN initiated copolymer of acrylonitrile with α -methyl styrene in presence (—) and absence (....) *p*-ABTAY.

Note

The effect of [*p*-ABTAY] on rate of propagation (R_p) has been examined by studying the possibility of formation of a complex between *p*-ABTAY and monomer using UV spectrum which suggests that the tendency of complex formation is nil hence R_p as well as R_t are unaffected. This leads to a conclusion that acceleration effect of *p*-ABTAY is due to the decrease of rate of termination which is further confirmed by non-linearity of the graph plotted between $\log R_p/R_{p0}$ and $\log \eta/\eta_0$ where R_{p0} and η_0 are the rate of polymerization and intrinsic viscosity in absence of [*p*-ABTAY], respectively.

The IR spectra of copolymer (Fig. 1) of α -MS with AN in presence and absence of ylide are identical and consists of following bands.

(i) The band at 2920 cm^{-1} is due to C-H stretching vibrations.

(ii) A strong band at 2240 cm^{-1} is due to $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group.

(iii) The C-H bending vibrations due to methyl and methylene group appear at $1340, 1440, 1490\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

(iv) The C-H bending band due to phenyl ring appears at 700 and 760 cm^{-1} .

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